

The 'World' Across Coffee-Houses

The Case for Conviviality: Public sphere and Cosmopolitan praxis in the writings of Mirza Abu Talib Isfahani

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Abstract

This essay aims to explore the histories of the public sphere and ideas of cosmopolitanism from a 'global perspective', as they emerged with the closure of the eighteenth and the beginning of the nineteenth century. This period is crucial to understanding imaginations and practices of the same because in this period, the universalism of European cosmopolitanism was faced by the utilitarianism of imperialism abroad for industrial modernity within. So far, in the cannon of modern intellectual history, ideas of cosmopolitanism have been traced back to Kant. In pointing out the Eurocentric bias of such a vision, postcolonial critiques have questioned the very ideals of the Enlightenment and paved way for politico-cultural provincialisms. To avoid such trappings, I will examine the writings of late eighteenth century scholar-traveler Mirza Abu Taleb who wrote extensively of his travels across Europe and West Asia between 1799-1803. By focusing on his comparison of coffee-house cultures across London, Paris and Istanbul, I shall destabilise Saidian notions of Orient and Occident. Thus reapproaching the Habermasian analysis of the public sphere that was limited only to European coffee-houses, that did not take into account and comparison the Ottoman and Arabic coffee cultures, this paper shall reclaim

the concerns of Kantian cosmopolitanism, albeit from a decolonial perspective, and finally argue that a global historical approach can make way for both multiplicity and the enlightenment universalism which is at the core of much of the modern world.

Keywords: Imperialism, Decolonial, Cosmopolitanism, Enlightenment, Public Sphere, South Asia, Travel Writing.

Introduction

Coffee-house is free to all Comers, so they have Humane shape, where a Liquor made of an Arabian Berry called Coffee is drunk. Six or seven years ago was it first brought into England, when the Palats of the English were as Fanatical, as their Brains. Like Apes, the English imitate all other people in their ridiculous Fashions. As Slaves they submit to the Customs even of Turkey and India. Doth the Frenchman wear Feathers in his Hat, and Pantaloons to hide his straddling? Believe it, the Englishman will be a la mode de France. With the Barbarous Indian he smokes Tobacco. With the Turk he drinks Coffee. A character of Coffee and Coffee-Houses, by M. P., 1661 A.D.¹

The above excerpt from a 17th century English treatise on Coffee Houses would seem peculiar to the lay person in the times of contemporary globalization when even in Communist China, people go to Starbucks for coffee. It might seem stranger even to the people of ‘The West,’ where Coffee-houses are an intrinsic part of the urban landscape, making cities like Paris unimaginable without its Cafés. The very same caricatured image is reproduced within pop culture by films like ‘Midnight in Paris’ – people sitting at numerous cafes, sipping coffee, smoking, and talking about all the on goings of politics and art – which takes up the aspirational

¹ "A character of coffee and coffee-houses by M.P." In the digital collection *Early English Books Online*. <https://name.umdl.umich.edu/A56639.0001.001>. University of Michigan Library Digital Collections.

imagination of ‘culture’ in the minds of young people in postcolonial Calcutta.² The comment on the British emulating the Turks in drinking coffee would seem even stranger to people in the postcolonial world – where Coffee is a cash crop representing the uneven development of capitalism and a luxury produced from the invisible exploitation of labourers in plantations, a remnant of European colonialism. Yet, the production of coffee, and coffee drinking as a social act did not have a ‘Western’ origin. European travellers first encountered coffee and coffee houses in Constantinople, between the late 16th and early 17th centuries,³ the word Coffee itself being derived from the Turkish ‘*kaveh*’. Ali Al-e Dawud also gives an informative account of Coffee Houses which proliferated and flourished in Persia during the Safavid times.⁴ It seemed like a place for intellectual discussions among scholars, Sufis, and even high-ranking officials, and at the same time a place for performance for poets and artists. The 17th century travel writer and Fellow of the Royal Society John Fryer noted that the Persians were very particular about their coffee, and they would spend time in the coffee houses for both leisure and business: he even compared the coffee houses to English theatres, as a place where poetry and entertainment had as much import as news.⁵

It becomes significant then, to think of the theoretical impact that these histories might have – because the Coffee House is one of the central motifs in Jürgen Habermas’s reading about the emergence of the ‘Public Sphere’ in 18th century Europe, especially England. Habermas looks at the coffee house as a discursive space, where private individuals met on a neutral ground to discuss, and debate matters of society and politics and reach a rational conclusion about the same – thereby making public opinion.⁶ Habermas’s proposition of ‘rational debate’ between ‘rational individuals’ towards the formation of a greater collective makes obvious the Kantian

² In his essay on Adda (casual conversation) in Bengal, Dipesh Chakrabarty shows how indigenous forms of conversation such as adda, while having its own history, tried to ‘civilise’ itself in early 20th century Calcutta by imitating European Café culture. The homogenizing tendency of modernity still continues to perpetuate the same in middle class aspirations of public conversations which can be seen through the proliferation of a certain kind of cafeteria aesthetic. See Chakrabarty, Dipesh. "Chapter 7. Adda: A History of Sociality" In *Provincializing Europe: Postcolonial Thought and Historical Difference - New Edition*, 180-213. Princeton: Princeton University Press, 2008. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9781400828654-010>.

³ Ellis, Markman. “The Wine of Islam Discovered.” In *The Coffee House: A Cultural History*, 19–27. Orion Publishing, 2011.

⁴ Ali Āl-E Dāwūd. “Coffeehouse.” Encyclopaedia Iranica, December 15, 1992. <https://www.iranicaonline.org/articles/coffeehouse-qahva-kana>.

⁵ Fryer, John. “New Account of East India and Persia Vol.3.” 34-35. Internet Archive, January 1, 1672. <https://archive.org/details/in.gov.ignca.6071/page/n47/mode/2up>.

⁶ Jürgen Habermas, ‘The Public Sphere’, in *Jürgen Habermas on Society and Politics: A Reader*, ed. Steven Seidman (Boston: Beacon Press, 1989).

underpinnings of the same.⁷ While Habermas places the development of the ‘rational public sphere’ in Europe and especially 18th century England, the fact that coffee as not just a commodity but also that the Coffee House as a phenomenon was encountered in the Ottoman Empire and then imported to Europe, points to the obvious development of a kind of public sphere, or rather, public culture in the Ottoman Empire during the 16th and 17th century. The lack of print capitalism and the specifics of bourgeoisie society in the Ottoman Empire at that time did not fit the normative form of a Habermasian public sphere that according to Habermas was ‘attained in England, France and to some extent in Germany after the Enlightenment.’⁸ Yet, if questions of the public sphere are approached without the presuppositions of this particularist form of ‘Enlightenment rationality,’⁹ it is interesting to notice that the Ottoman Coffee House did offer a public space where socio-cultural performance met political concern. In such a place, to differentiate between rational critique, and critique in a theatrically performative form such as political satire lends to nothing more than denying the nature of this particularist difference, which ends up reinforcing the normative form of the Habermasian public sphere.¹⁰

By recognizing the discourse of intellectual and political exchange characterising European Coffeeshouses as a form of Kantian cosmopolitanism, and the place of Kant in the canon of ideas of cosmopolitanism, in this essay I shall reapproach the Habermasian analysis of the public sphere that was limited only to European coffee-houses. To address the problem of the Eurocentric normative history of the public sphere and the conceptual limitation it creates, I will examine the writings of late eighteenth century scholar-traveller Mirza Abu Talib, focusing especially on Talib’s comparison of coffee-house cultures across London, Paris and Istanbul, about which he wrote extensively in the record of his travels across Europe and West Asia between 1799-1803. Born around 1752 into a Persianate service elite straddling the courtly worlds of Lucknow and Murshidabad in eighteenth century Mughal India, Mirza Abu Talib Khan

⁷ Kant: Idea for a universal history from a cosmopolitan point of View. Accessed April 27, 2025. <https://www.marxists.org/reference/subject/ethics/kant/universal-history.htm>. See the second, fourth and fifth thesis.

⁸ Siviloglu, Murat R. *The Emergence of Public Opinion: State and Society in the late Ottoman Empire*, 13-20. Cambridge, United Kingdom: Cambridge University Press, 2020.

Karababa, Emnegül, and Gülz Ger. “Early Modern Ottoman Coffeehouse Culture and the Formation of the Consumer Subject.” *Journal of Consumer Research* 37, no. 5 (February 1, 2011): 737–60. <https://doi.org/10.1086/656422>.

⁹ Here I am noting Enlightenment rationality as a historically produced and ideologically specific project, and not as an abstract form which might be traced cross-culturally despite of, and within local cultural peculiarities.

¹⁰ Kömeçoğlu, Uğur. “The Publicness and Sociabilities of the Ottoman Coffeehouse.” *Javnost - The Public* 12, no. 2 (January 2005): 5–22. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13183222.2005.11008885>.

was educated in the Indo-Persian intellectual tradition and served in administrative roles under both the remnants of the Mughal state and the expanding East India Company. His family history was marked by political turbulence, and his own career reflected the uncertainties of a time when Mughal sovereignty was giving way to British dominance. In 1799, facing diminished prospects, he accepted an offer from his English friend, David Thomas Richardson, to journey to Britain. Over the next four years, Abu Talib travelled through the Indian Ocean and Cape of Good Hope to England and Ireland, and returned via Southern Europe, the Ottoman Empire, and Persia—finally arriving in Calcutta in 1803. His Persian travelogue—later translated into English as *Travels of Mirza Abu Talib Khan*—is a remarkable document that blends ethnographic observation, political commentary, and philosophical reflection. Far from conforming to the epistemic binaries of colonial Orientalism, Abu Talib’s work exhibits a historically grounded cosmopolitanism. He engages not only with the curiosities and spectacles of Europe, but with its political institutions, economic structures, and sociability—offering both appreciation and critique. His ambition for a universal history, expressed in works like *Lubb-us-Siyar*, places Islamic, European, and even American histories within a shared world-historical horizon, underscoring his commitment to global enquiry beyond civilizational essentialism.¹¹

By bringing Abu Talib’s accounts of the Ottoman coffee cultures into comparison with their European counterparts, this paper destabilises Saidian notions of Orient and Occident, and reapproaches the concerns of Kantian cosmopolitanism from a decolonial perspective, testing it against what Walter Mignolo has called *decolonial cosmopolitanism*: a vision of planetary conviviality not grounded in European universals, but articulated through the ‘pluriversal’ experiences of those historically positioned “on the other side of the line.”¹² Finally, I shall read Abu Talib’s comparativist view of coffee-house cultures through Gurminder Bhambra’s framework of *connected sociologies*, in which she argues against multiple modernities confronting each other but rather calls for the study of a global modernity that must be understood through reconstructing dominant universal concepts such as ‘cosmopolitanism’ and its manifestation through obfuscated histories.¹³ It is achieved not just by fitting such histories

¹¹ Hasan, Mushirul. “Resistance And Acquiescence In North India: Muslim Responses To The West.” *Rivista Degli Studi Orientali* 67, no. 1/2 (1993): 83–105. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/41880771>.

¹² Mignolo, Walter. “The Many Faces of Cosmo-Polis.” *The Politics of Decolonial Investigations*, July 9, 2021, 181–228. <https://doi.org/10.1215/9781478002574-008>.

¹³ Bhambra, Gurminder K. *Connected Sociologies*, 1-16. London, England: Bloomsbury Academic, 2015.

into the existing theories, but by re-theorizing existing theoretical concepts from the vantage point of these histories. To address this, I will place Abu Talib's commentary on coffee-house cultures and cosmopolitanism within a history of the public sphere and ideas of cosmopolitanism from a 'global perspective', as they emerged with the closure of the eighteenth and the beginning of the nineteenth century. This period is crucial to understanding imaginations and practices of the same because in this period, the universalisation of European political imaginations and social ordering was achieved through the expansion of the imperial reach of the British and French empires – which at the same time were confronted by the differences of social conditions in the many colonies across the world, further perpetuated by the politics of imperialism.¹⁴ In pointing out the Eurocentric bias of such a vision, postcolonial critiques have questioned the very ideals of the Enlightenment and paved way for politico-cultural provincialisms, which focused on culturalist reactions to European colonialism.¹⁵ Yet, even if the values of modern civilization were denied to the colonies, in turn imperial governance of the British was critiqued by the Orientalists and figures like Edmund Burke who argued for the cultural specificities of the British colonies and tried to affirm their coevalness with British culture. Strangely enough, Burke's critique of British imperialism mirrors the postcolonial critique of the same – the British civilizing mission's tendency to locate and identify colonial society on a general schema of societal development, dubbed as the "cosmopolitanism of reason," is pit against Burke's "cosmopolitanism of sentiments" which is predicated upon "recognition" of the "sentiments, feelings and sense of location" formed by the religious, archaic and premodern society of India.¹⁶

This fails to identify how people in the colonies encountered the realities of colonialism and Europe, adopting, transforming and responding to the 'enlightened' concepts of 'European civilization' and the realities they represented. Abu Talib's reflections are not composed at a distance but formed through a process of bodily and intellectual traversal from the Indo-Persianate world he was familiar with to imperial metropolises of Europe and the varied rhythms of these public cultures. His movements generated a deeply reflexive mode of

¹⁴ Mehta, Uday Singh. *Liberalism and Empire: A Study in Nineteenth-Century British Liberal Thought*, 2-8. University of Chicago Press, 1999.

¹⁵ Carey, Daniel, and Sven Trakulhun, 'Universalism, Diversity, and the Postcolonial Enlightenment', in Daniel Carey, and Lynn Festa (eds), *The Postcolonial Enlightenment: Eighteenth-Century Colonialism and Postcolonial Theory* (Oxford, 2013; online edn, Oxford Academic, 3 Mar. 2015), <https://doi.org/10.1093/acprof:osobl/9780199677597.003.0008>.

¹⁶ Mehta, Uday Singh. *Liberalism and Empire: A Study in Nineteenth-Century British Liberal Thought*, 17-23. University of Chicago Press, 1999.

comparison – one that registered not just cultural differences, but the shared forms of sociability, critique, and deliberation embedded in urban coffeehouse life. His writing becomes a historical enactment of Ulrich Beck’s formulation of *methodological cosmopolitanism*.¹⁷ Beck calls for a decisive shift away from normative, nation-state-centred understandings of society and towards a recognition of the embodied, lived experiences of individuals who move through and negotiate multiple cultural worlds. Rather than abstract ideals, cosmopolitanism for Beck is grounded in *bodily encounters* – it is a way of being-in-the-world that emerges from the affective, sensory, and reflexive navigation of entangled global spaces. This is not merely about inhabiting different locations, but about encountering and internalising the contradictions, connections, and uneven proximities that constitute modern life. Such cosmopolitanism is not disembodied, but enacted through practices, movements, and negotiations with difference. It is through this lens that we might approach Abu Talib, whose journey across the metropolises of Eurasia renders him not merely an observer of Europe, but a historical actor shaped by the cosmopolitan condition he experiences thus theorising cosmopolitanism by transcending particularistic barriers.

To demonstrate all of this, I will proceed to answer the following question: If the European/British Coffee House is a distinctive cultural space with a set of discursive practices that led to the development of the bourgeois public sphere in England, France and Germany in the 18th century, then how does an ‘Oriental’ character – the Indo-Iranian traveller Mirza Abu Talib – engage with such spaces in his travels across Europe, and understand public culture and cosmopolitanism, given that he was familiar with the coffee-houses of Delhi in Mughal India where people gathered to discuss matters of culture and society?¹⁸ For this, let us consider one of the most notable features of the English Coffee Houses – the reading and circulation of journals and newspapers. Among the various kinds of papers produced in Coffee House encounters in London,¹⁹ there were *The Tatler*, *The Guardian* (still active and currently one of the most popular newspapers read not just in the UK but across the English-speaking world) and *The Spectator*. To quote Joseph Addison writing in *The Spectator*, in March 1711,

¹⁷ Beck, Ulrich. “Mobility and the Cosmopolitan Perspective.” *Exploring Networked Urban Mobilities*, October 20, 2017, 140–51. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315201078-9>.

¹⁸ Blake, Stephen P. *Shahjahanabad: The sovereign city in Mughal India, 1639-1739*, 55-57. Cambridge England: Cambridge University Press, 2002.

¹⁹ Ellis, Markman. “The Philosopher in the Coffee-House.” In *The Coffee House: A Cultural History*, 134–147. Orion Publishing, 2011.

It was said of Socrates, that he brought Philosophy down from Heaven, to inhabit among Men, and I shall be ambitious to have it said of me, that I have brought Philosophy out of Closets and Libraries, Schools and Colleges, to dwell in Clubs and Assemblies, at Tea-Tables and in Coffee-houses.²⁰

In fact, as Ellis notes, these publications were trying to not just circulate ideas and happenings and help discussion, but also a notion of civility – the cultivation of a higher form of ‘politeness’ is to improve ‘human nature.’²¹ Habermas also notes the same about English Coffee Houses in London:

When Addison and Steele published the first issue of the *Tatler* in 1709, the coffee houses were already so numerous and the circles of their frequenters already so wide that contact among these thousand-fold circles could only be maintained through a journal. At the same time, the new periodical was so intimately interwoven with the life of the coffee houses that the individual issues were indeed sufficient basis for its reconstruction. The periodical articles were not only made the object of discussion by the public of the coffee houses but were viewed as integral parts of this discussion; this was demonstrated by the flood of letters from which the editor each week published a selection. When the *Spectator* separated from the *Guardian* the letters to the editor were provided with a special institution: on the west side of Button’s Coffee House a lion’s head was attached through whose jaws the reader threw his letter.²²

²⁰ Addison, Joseph. “The Spectator, Issue 10, Monday, March 12, 1711.” *Literature in Context*. Accessed April 22, 2025. <https://anthologydev.lib.virginia.edu/work/Spectator/addison-spectator-10>.

²¹ Once again, this invokes, or rather, pre-empts Kant’s vision of cosmopolitan civilization.

²² Habermas, Jürgen. *The Structural Transformation of the Public Sphere: An Inquiry into a category of Bourgeois Society*, 42. Cambridge: Polity Press, 1989.

Thus, what emerged in this space might be termed as a ‘republic of letters.’²³ On this count, let us turn to Abu Talib’s comment on the printing of newspapers and subsequent circulation of newspapers in the English Coffee Houses that cut across classes, giving evidence of broad readership:

Of the inventions of Europe, the utility of which may not appear at first sight to an Asiatic, the art of printing is the most admirable. By its aid, thousands of copies, of any scientific, moral, or religious book, may be circulated among the people in a very short time; and by it, the works of celebrated authors are handed down to posterity, free from the errors and imperfections of a manuscript. To this art the English are indebted for the humble but useful publication of Newspapers, without which life would be irksome to them. These are read by all ranks of people, from the prince to the beggar. They are printed daily and sent every morning to the houses of the rich; but those who cannot afford to subscribe for one, go and read them at the coffee-rooms or public-houses.²⁴

Touching upon the ‘Utility of the Art of Printing,’ Abu Talib goes on to explain that these newspapers could be accessed by any person, and they contain information of everything happening in the world – events and matters of political significance, the economy, and cultural happenings.²⁵ Abu Talib’s appreciation of the English Coffee House is, therefore, remarkably like what Habermas is pointing to – it is based on the utilitarian advantage of spreading knowledge, civility and promoting discussion in society. This becomes even more interesting if read against Abu Talib’s own intention in writing his travelogue, which he stated to be so in the Introduction:

²³ Solleveld, Floris. "Afterlives of the Republic of Letters: Learned Journals and Scholarly Community in the Early Nineteenth Century", *Erudition and the Republic of Letters* 5, 1 (2020): 82-116, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1163/24055069-00501003>.

I’m calling it a ‘republic of letters’ because access to this world of discourse was still limited by access to newspapers and coffeehouses – the ‘demise’, or rather transformation of the ‘republic’ into the modern world of the dissemination of knowledge was built through institutions and the standardization of learning and spread of literacy which became much more widespread in the second half of the nineteenth century.

²⁴ Abu Talib ibn Muhammad, Isfahani, (Daniel O’Quinn, and Charles Stewart). *The travels of Mirza Abu Talib Khan in Asia, Africa and Europe, during the years 1799, 1800, 1801, 1802, and 1803.*, 157. Peterborough, Ontario: Broadview, 2009.

²⁵ Abu Talib ibn Muhammad, Isfahani, (Daniel O’Quinn, and Charles Stewart). *The travels of Mirza Abu Talib Khan in Asia, Africa and Europe, during the years 1799, 1800, 1801, 1802, and 1803.*, 157-158. Peterborough, Ontario: Broadview, 2009.

It therefore occurred to him, that if he were to write all the circumstances of his journey through Europe, to describe the curiosities and wonders which he saw, and to give some account of the manners and customs of the various nations he visited...many of the customs, inventions, sciences, and ordinances of Europe, the good effects of which are apparent in those countries, might with great advantage, be imitated by the Mohammendans.²⁶

This evinces three things – a curiosity of the unknown, the willingness to familiarize and understand, and a desire to spread knowledge. Once again, we may locate a Kantian notion of cosmopolitan civilizational aspirations working beneath such an impetus as a logic, just as it does in discursive practices of English Coffee Houses and Habermas’s reading of the same. One might even want to consider that not many years after Abu Talib’s sojourn, Mīrzā Muhammad Ṣāliḥ Shīrāzī, one of the five Persian students who studied in England between 1815 to 1819 under the patronage of Abbas Mirza, crown prince of Iran, learnt the ‘art of printing’, brought back with him a printing machine to Persia. In 1837, Shīrāzī printed the first Persian newspaper – the ‘Khagaz-i-Shirazi’.²⁷ The same can also be noticed in India: in 1822, Raja Rammohan Roy started the weekly Persian newsletter ‘Mīrat-ul-Akhbar’,²⁸ which was published every week. The fact that these were published in Persian makes it obvious that Shīrāzī and Roy believed that there would be readership for printed media in the larger Indo-Persianate world. One might make the case for technological transmission from Europe, but against that, one can as easily argue that printing technology was first invented in China in the 11th century A.D. from where it travelled to Europe. Besides, technological determinism is suggestive of a linear conception of history caught within the telos of ‘development’ – rather, the making and usage of the printing press in 15th century Europe and early 19th century Persia and South Asia is part of larger societal processes already unfolding in these places, and the printing press as a technology and social phenomenon

²⁶ Abu Talib ibn Muhammad, Isfahani, (Daniel O’Quinn, and Charles Stewart). *The travels of Mirza Abu Talib Khan in Asia, Africa and Europe, during the years 1799, 1800, 1801, 1802, and 1803.*, 59. Peterborough, Ontario: Broadview, 2009.

²⁷ Green, Nile. “Journeymen, Middlemen: Travel, Transculture, and Technology in the Origins of Muslim Printing.” *International Journal of Middle East Studies* 41, no. 2 (2009): 203–24. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/40206102>.

²⁸ Codell, Julie F. “Introduction: The Nineteenth-Century News from India.” *Victorian Periodicals Review* 37, no. 2 (2004): 106–23. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/20084001>.

become both symptomatic and emblematic of the unfolding of aforementioned societal processes.²⁹

Coupled with this, the fact that Abu Talib was writing for an audience back at home (even if he was cynical about the possible reception of his work and readership) gives further evidence to the fact that among a certain class of people in the Indo-Persianate world, realizing the possibility of a sphere of intellectual discussion on society and politics at large between individuals, was not a strange occurrence.³⁰ Habermas has noted that the ‘republic of letters’ formed around English coffee houses and French salons had a problem of exclusion which might be linked to education and class-based opportunities, but he also noted that the ideal of the acceptance and debate between people and ideas, regardless of differences in power was ingrained in the making of such spaces.³¹ This also echoes what Ellis notes about the writing and circulation of newsletters and magazines in coffeehouses and how an ‘idea of civility’ operated in its functioning.³² Yet, what remains and becomes important in the case of Mirza Abu Talib and the European Enlightenment, is the idea of a utopia, where strangeness, both in terms of strangers/people and as ideas, can be encountered, debated, and accepted through mediation. This is at the centre of the globalizing drive of European modernity – to create a ‘world’ of ‘universal civilization’. Through a character like Mirza Abu Talib, and especially his understanding of Coffee Houses between London, Paris, Constantinople and Baghdad, it becomes apparent that it is possible to locate the drive to realise such a world order on a shared notion of civilizational values that was not local to Europe, but ‘Global’ despite of particularities. To ascertain this, let us look at what Abu Talib had to say about the Coffee Houses in Paris, Istanbul, and Baghdad, and what can be drawn out of his conclusions on them.

In Paris, Abu Talib notes:

²⁹ “The Technology and the Society (1974).” *Raymond Williams on Culture and Society: Essential Writings*, 2014, 139–60. <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781473914766.n9>.

³⁰ I’m borrowing from C.A. Bayly’s characterisation of pre-colonial India as a ‘literacy-aware society’. Bayly, C.A. “Prologue: Surveillance and communication in early modern India.” In *Empire and Information: Intelligence gathering and social communication in India, 1780-1870*, 39. Cambridge University Press, 1996.

³¹ “Not that this idea of the ‘public’ was realised in earnest in the coffee houses, the *salons*, and the societies; but as an idea it had become institutionalized and thereby stated as an objective claim. If not realised, it was at least consequential” (Habermas 1989).

³² Ellis, Markman. “The Philosopher in the Coffee-House.” In *The Coffee House: A Cultural History*, 134–147. Orion Publishing, 2011.

In Paris, the coffee-houses are innumerable, but in general are very filthy; and as many of the French smoke segars or cheroots in them at all hours of the day, they smell shockingly of tobacco. A person is also much annoyed by beggars at these places: they follow a gentleman into the room and sometimes even take hold of his hand, to move his compassion, or rather to tire him by their importunity: they are, however, content with a trifle, and will sometimes be satisfied by a piece of bread: to obtain this favour, they have frequently to contend with a surly rival, in the form of a dog, whose filth is lying about in different parts of the room.³³

One might at the very onset notice his dislike of begging and be reminded of his critique of the same in context of Awadh – thus it is not a simple matter of denigrating the French in favour of the British. The mode of his critique though, becomes even more telling when one is to look at his impression at Coffee Houses in Constantinople:

The coffee-house and barbers' shops in this city are innumerable. The Turks, though very indolent, are not fond of retirement or solitude: they, therefore, immediately after breakfast, go to one of these places, where they sit smoking, drinking coffee or sherbet, and listening to idle stories, the whole day. Their conversations are carried on in a loud tone of voice, and sometimes eight or ten persons talk at the same time; it is therefore impossible for a foreigner to understand what they are saying; and, in short, the societies of these coffee-houses are little better than an assembly of brutes. The rooms are also exceedingly dirty and seldom afford anything but thick coffee, and tobacco cheroots or pipes.³⁴

In the case of both Paris, and Constantinople, the Coffee Houses are dirty, and full of smokers, with a general unwelcoming veneer. This is also the case in Baghdad: "Baghdad abounds with

³³ Abu Talib ibn Muhammad, Isfahani, (Daniel O'Quinn, and Charles Stewart). *The travels of Mirza Abu Talib Khan in Asia, Africa and Europe, during the years 1799, 1800, 1801, 1802, and 1803.*, 242. Peterborough, Ontario: Broadview, 2009.

³⁴ Abu Talib ibn Muhammad, Isfahani, (Daniel O'Quinn, and Charles Stewart). *The travels of Mirza Abu Talib Khan in Asia, Africa and Europe, during the years 1799, 1800, 1801, 1802, and 1803.*, 280. Peterborough, Ontario: Broadview, 2009.

coffee-houses, and rooms for smoking tobacco; but are even darker and filthier than those of Constantinople.”³⁵ The general critique of filth is something he also extends to the entire city of Baghdad, and the inns of Constantinople, which are: “Horrid places, the only good accommodation for a traveller in this city is at the French and English hotels in Galata.”³⁶

On this note, it is interesting to notice how Paris, Constantinople and Baghdad are placed in one coordinate when it comes to Coffee House cultures, whereas when it comes to hospitable places in Constantinople for a stranger, Abu Talib says that it is French and English hotels that are most welcoming. This breaks down the East-West binary ingrained in Saidian histories of Asia-Europe encounters. While all the Coffee Houses promote a culture of socialization, French and Ottoman Coffee Houses become sites that are unwelcoming due to filth and tobacco smoke, and also because the Ottomans converse in a manner that excludes the stranger. In comparison, English coffeehouses served as welcoming spaces where individuals gathered to socialize while reading newspapers and exchanging news and ideas. According to Abu Talib, this atmosphere encouraged participation and made it easier for strangers to feel included. This also recalls his comment on the Irish on the matter of acceptance and hospitality: “In...hospitality and prodigality, freedom of speech and open heartedness, they surpass the English and the Scotch...the landlady and her children soon comprehended my broken English...”³⁷

and how they went out of their way to “make themselves useful” to a foreign stranger.³⁸ In contrast, Paris, and to a greater degree, Constantinople, fail to inculcate a concourse of different people who can share ideas and mediate difference, thus becoming unwelcoming as places to Abu Talib. By making a stranger such as Abu Talib unwelcome, the figure of the stranger in the Coffee House becomes merely ornamental – a token gesture that becomes a metaphor for multicultural coexistences of cultures which are not in dialogue. Through his critique of the

³⁵ Abu Talib ibn Muhammad, Isfahani, (Daniel O’Quinn, and Charles Stewart). *The travels of Mirza Abu Talib Khan in Asia, Africa and Europe, during the years 1799, 1800, 1801, 1802, and 1803.*, 350. Peterborough, Ontario: Broadview, 2009.

³⁶ Abu Talib ibn Muhammad, Isfahani, (Daniel O’Quinn, and Charles Stewart). *The travels of Mirza Abu Talib Khan in Asia, Africa and Europe, during the years 1799, 1800, 1801, 1802, and 1803.*, 280. Peterborough, Ontario: Broadview, 2009.

³⁷ Abu Talib ibn Muhammad, Isfahani, (Daniel O’Quinn, and Charles Stewart). *The travels of Mirza Abu Talib Khan in Asia, Africa and Europe, during the years 1799, 1800, 1801, 1802, and 1803.*, 111. Peterborough, Ontario: Broadview, 2009.

³⁸ Abu Talib ibn Muhammad, Isfahani, (Daniel O’Quinn, and Charles Stewart). *The travels of Mirza Abu Talib Khan in Asia, Africa and Europe, during the years 1799, 1800, 1801, 1802, and 1803.*, 111. Peterborough, Ontario: Broadview, 2009.

ornamental figure of the foreigner in the Coffee-houses of Paris and Constantinople as opposed to the ones in London from a position that valorises encounters between strangers and a convivial exchange of knowledge (as exemplified by his description of the Irish whom he contrasted with the English and the Scots), Abu Talib makes a case for universal abstract notions of hospitality and cosmopolitanism that he realised through his praxis of travel and encountering strangeness.

While Abu Talib's critique of the French has been read as evidence of his imbibing the cultural stereotypes given by the British,³⁹ with whom it is easy to imagine a certain kind of collusion on his part, there is much that he said that can contradict such a reading. The lack of a circulation in knowledge in both France and Ottoman Turkey, is something that Abu Talib critiques based on the fundamental purpose of the pursuit and circulation of knowledge and understanding of the world, which are the motivations for him to undertake his journey and to record his sightings and findings in writing for others to read. This may also shed light on the comment on Turkish 'indolence' – indolence is not an essentialist character that Abu Talib assigns. In fact, he critiques it among his countrymen: *"The want of energy and the indolent dispositions of my countrymen, and the many erroneous customs which exist..."*⁴⁰

Most importantly, echoes of the same are found in the critique that he offers on the character of the English:

The fourth of their frailties is a desire of ease, and a dislike to exertion...it prevents them from perfecting themselves in science and exerting themselves in the services of their friends...the sixth defect of the English is their throwing away their time...⁴¹

³⁹ Smith, Blake. 2018. "The French are weak degenerates: An Indian voyager's account from Paris in early 19th century." *Scroll.in.* <https://scroll.in/magazine/865107/the-french-are-apatetic-and-feeble-an-indian-voyagers-account-from-paris-in-early-19th-century>.

⁴⁰ Abu Talib ibn Muhammad, Isfahani, (Daniel O'Quinn, and Charles Stewart). *The travels of Mirza Abu Talib Khan in Asia, Africa and Europe, during the years 1799, 1800, 1801, 1802, and 1803.*, 59. Peterborough, Ontario: Broadview, 2009.

⁴¹ Abu Talib ibn Muhammad, Isfahani, (Daniel O'Quinn, and Charles Stewart). *The travels of Mirza Abu Talib Khan in Asia, Africa and Europe, during the years 1799, 1800, 1801, 1802, and 1803.*, 209. Peterborough, Ontario: Broadview, 2009.

In this broad critique of the English character based on what Abu Talib identifies as their desire for ease, (lining up with his critique of Turkish indolence), it is possible to locate Abu Talib's critique of the shallow quality of British engagement with Indian knowledge systems, as well as their failure to be as good in friendship as the Irish. This is done based on the same reasons he gives to explain the unwelcoming propensity of the Ottoman coffee houses to both strangers and knowledge, and the general decay of society in India. By focusing on knowledge, and how indolence is antithetical to the pursuit of the same, we can locate Abu Talib's pursuit of knowledge within an Islamic tradition of travelogues genres of *safarnama* and *rihla* as a way of venturing into the 'unknown'. These genres were marked by conception of curiosity and a drive to understand the 'natural world' – thus placing his travelogue on the same plane as that of its counterparts in Enlightenment humanism.

Finally, through the conscious act of travelling, knowing and engaging with what is strange or foreign, Abu Talib creates a framework of engaging with the world through certain values that cut across cultural lines and are applicable anywhere, thus making way for both multiplicity and the Enlightenment universalism. It is through this system that Abu Talib's critique of the Coffee Houses in Paris, Constantinople and Baghdad, and his preference of the same in case of the British must be understood. In establishing so, not only do I ascertain his critique and worldview as cosmopolitan – but through his focus on understanding and the stress on knowledge, the vision of an 18th century Indo-Persian intellectual converges seamlessly with the European Enlightenment's vision of knowledge and planetary cosmopolitanism. At the same time, this also answers Walter Mignolo's call for "decolonial cosmopolitanism(s)"⁴² which calls for engaging with knowledge from the 'margins': by analysing the writings of Mirza Abu Talib, a character from the colonial periphery, or 'margins' of the British Empire, not only do we find evidence of an exemplary praxis of cosmopolitanism from a non-western tradition, but it is also clear that Abu Talib himself did not operate within a mould of 'metropole and colony.' Abu Talib's writings neither exoticize nor idealize; rather, he recognised in these transregional coffeehouse cultures a shared potential for public deliberation and sociability. Thus, Abu Talib unsettles the neat opposition between the 'cosmopolitanism of reason,' which presumes the universal

⁴² Mignolo, Walter. "The Many Faces of Cosmo-Polis." *The Politics of Decolonial Investigations*, July 9, 2021, 181–228. <https://doi.org/10.1215/9781478002574-008>.

applicability of abstract norms, and the ‘cosmopolitanism of sentiments,’ which rests on affective recognition of cultural particularity. Abu Talib’s thought and practice move through and beyond this binary. His appreciation of the rational institutions of English public life –especially the coffeehouse and the newspaper –reveals his commitment to reasoned enquiry and universal ideas of sociability and improvement. Yet, this is never detached from an ethical attentiveness to context, sentiment, and embodied experience: whether in his critique of the exclusionary noise of Ottoman coffeehouses or his praise for Irish warmth and generosity, his judgments are always mediated by the relational ethos of travel and dialogue, making Abu Talib a practitioner of “methodological cosmopolitanism.”⁴³ In this sense, Abu Talib offers a mode of cosmopolitanism in which reason and sentiment are not opposed but braided –each grounding the other in his vision of a world where knowledge, hospitality, and self-reflection are shared civic virtues. In doing so, Abu Talib reorients the discourse of cosmopolitanism by demonstrating that such forms of theorising public life and cosmopolitanism were not exclusive to Europe, nor did they originate there in isolation, but through historical encounters shaped by the currents of imperialist globalisation.

In this regard, Mirza Abu Talib’s theoretical engagement with cosmopolitanism offers a compelling instantiation of what Gurinder Bhambra identifies as the need for *connected sociologies* –a mode of social analysis that recognises global modernity as the product of shared, imperial, and interconnected histories rather than as an endogenous European achievement. Abu Talib’s travels unfolded during a moment of profound transformation, when imperial expansion, shifting commercial circuits, and new technologies of communication were bringing distant peoples and institutions into intensified contact. His reflections thus emerge not from the margins of modernity, but from within its formative, global processes. Crucially, Bhambra reminds us that such transformations –often attributed solely to internal European development –were in fact co-constituted through imperial entanglements that linked Britain, South Asia, the Ottoman world, and beyond. Abu Talib’s observations of coffeehouse cultures, and his comparative reflections on public discourse, sociability, and governance across cities like London, Paris, Constantinople, and Baghdad, exemplify how individuals from colonised or semi-colonial

⁴³ Beck, Ulrich. “Mobility and the Cosmopolitan Perspective.” *Exploring Networked Urban Mobilities*, October 20, 2017, 140–51. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315201078-9>.

societies were actively engaging with, interpreting, and contributing to these transformations. His writings make visible the very global interconnections that Bhabra argues social theory must foreground: rather than treating colonial actors as peripheral to the making of modernity, Abu Talib's account demands we situate them as central interlocutors in its intellectual and institutional formation. His cosmopolitanism is not an imitation of European reason, but a historically grounded expression of worldliness shaped by the very structures of empire that enabled his movements and reflections.

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